

Nano-NAMS DB – showcase of the first database dedicated to nano-specific alternative methods in human hazard and safety assessment under different EU regulations

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Abstract

The escalating utilization of Engineered Nanomaterials (ENMs) in a variety of consumer products necessitates the development of efficient and effective nano-specific methodologies for assessing potential hazards to human health and environment. Given the ethical, economic, and time-related challenges associated with animal testing, as well as emerging bans on such methods, it is paramount to develop and validate alternative methods, known as New Approach Methodologies (NAMs). However, the vast diversity of these methods and the regulations governing them call for the development of a strategy to categorize and catalogue them in an easily accessible repository. To date, there has been no comprehensive database collating all of the nanomaterial-related New Approach Methodologies under EU Regulations in one place. The objective of this presentation is to introduce the data collection and methodology for the categorization of NAMs under EU laws [1] and to showcase a newly developed Nano-NAMs database, designed to manage information on all developed nanomaterial-related NAMs [2] linked to AOPs and KEs.

References:

[1] ECHA, Nano-specific alternative methods in human hazard/safety assessment under different EU regulations, considering the animal testing bans already in place for cosmetics and their ingredient, https://euon.echa.europa.eu/view-article/-/journal_content/title/new-study-identifies-challenges-of-animal-free-test-methods-application-for-nanomaterials

[2] <https://nams.qsarlab.com/>